

PROBLEM OF EDUCATION OF SPEED-AGILITY QUALITIES IN WRESTLERS

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Abstract: The internationalization and as a result the strengthening of sports competitions in belt wrestling increases the importance of evaluating the quantitative and qualitative indicators of the competitive activity of the strongest wrestlers in the world in order to determine the development trends of the sport. and analyzed.

Key words: belt wrestling, technical-tactical skill, technical training, female wrestler, skill and skill, sports skill, highly skilled athlete.

INTRODUCTION

Many types of wrestling with national roots are recognized and popular in the world and are trying to get a place in the program of the Olympic Games. The ancient national wrestling of the Turkic peoples is considered belt wrestling. Today, the development of this type of wrestling is related to the expansion of its distribution geography, the increase in its international status, that is, the inclusion of sports that are not included in the Olympic sports, the inclusion of sports in the world network, and the strengthening of competition between high-level athletes.

Currently, belt wrestling is spread in 59 countries of the world, on 4 continents, and since 2002, world championships have been held regularly.

It is characterized by all the processes characteristic of the development of martial arts in the world, that is, the increase in achievements, high competition, the pursuit of maximum realization of individual physical capabilities and technical-tactical skills of athletes.

According to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4881 dated November 4, 2020, on measures to develop the national sport of wrestling and further increase its international prestige, the rich traditions and values of the wrestling sport inherited from our great ancestors will be passed on to the future. passing on to generations, increasing the role of wrestling in the world arena under the name of the Uzbek sports brand, strengthening the sense of patriotism among young people by supporting and encouraging their interest in national sports, all strata of the population, especially young people, as well as , it is planned to create the necessary conditions for the people of the world to practice this type of sport.

Today, it is impossible to train a highly qualified wrestler without knowing the trends in the development of wrestling, without determining the most effective ways and means of achieving high sports skills, without having serious scientific and methodological support.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

According to experts, the technique of individual wrestling sports is the main direction that ensures the formation of a highly qualified athlete during long-term training. The analysis of technical and tactical actions used by wrestlers in major competitions allows us to identify this type of sport.

To distinguish the technical and tactical characteristics of the strongest wrestlers, which influence the development trends of the wrestling technique and the result.

However, no matter how many favorite techniques a wrestler has, he should always strive to supplement his technique with new, well-developed techniques and variations of previously mastered technical moves. He will have to do this with one of the unique features of wrestling, which is that opponents will determine their opponent's strengths and weaknesses relatively quickly, after a few bouts. Technical diversity plays a major role in conducting the competition.

At the same time, it should be noted that the current level of achievement is impossible without individualizing the technical training of the athlete, taking into account the morphogenetic characteristics of his organism, where experts pay special attention to the lateralization of the motor and sensory systems. Also, it is important to take into account the gender characteristics of women wrestlers and their influence on competition. Taking into account the above, it is important to consider the issues of success of a wrestler who has mastered the technique of working on the right or left side.

Also, a comparative analysis of the competitive activity of highly qualified wrestlers, men and women, is required. Wrestling has been practiced in our country for many years. This sport is distinguished from other sports by the fact that wrestling is a popular sport, the attractiveness of the actions, and the teaching of children to act independently. In the child, his defense, attack, and tactics in his position encourage him to act responsibly. What should we pay attention to when managing the physical condition of young wrestlers: First, the coach should familiarize himself with the physical condition of children from the day they come to wrestling training;

Secondly, after checking the physical condition of the child, if the physical qualities are weak in development (strength, quickness, agility, endurance, flexibility), give him moderated exercises in this direction and control their uniform development. ; Thirdly, the formation of the technical skills of the child, in which individual characteristics, that is, the ability to fight, to have a unique character, forming the ability to make quick decisions in unexpected situations; Fourthly, it is important that the wrestler goes out with his partners, diligently follows the coach's instructions during training and adapts to the given techniques. Working with young wrestlers requires great skill from the coach. Working with each athlete individually, he should know his psychology well, adapt to training and develop his physical qualities in a row.

The specific indicators of the wrestlers' technique have been described by many experts, and different directions of their application have been defined. All this information requires the development of a system of technical indicators, without which it is impossible to effectively control various stages of sports training, to develop methods for predicting sports success, and to set the target tasks of program preparation. Cultivation of movement qualities is part of the process of uniform training. When we consider the method of improving the physical fitness of wrestlers, we first of all mean the methods of training physical qualities. The process of managing the physical condition of wrestlers is a very important process. All five qualities must be equally developed in wrestling. But it is necessary to take into account the condition of young wrestlers. The qualities of strength, agility, flexibility, quickness, endurance are developed through individual or general physical training.

Agility is a complex coordination ability, and it is difficult to find a single criterion for its assessment. the complexity of the tasks, its accurate and timely execution in the struggle, this time is the shortest time from changing the situation to the moment when the response action begins. The agility of young wrestlers is first of all manifested in offensive and defensive actions in the ever-changing situation of the wrestling field. In order to achieve a combination of agility and quickness in wrestlers and not to worsen the coordination capabilities and endurance, it is necessary to use such tools and methods of training that are in accordance with the requirements of movement activity of wrestlers. It is very important to select special running exercises, movement exercises with different loads, and use a strictly ordered exercise method, in particular, the method of repetition, the method of continuous standard exercises, in training the qualities of agility in wrestlers.

During training, young wrestlers are required to demonstrate agility in a short period of time. Various exercises (15-20 second knockdown, short distance

running, 4x4 mokky running) are effective means of improving the agility of wrestlers. Special agility exercises are used to run 4x4 and knock down the opponent in 20-25 seconds. In order to improve the qualities of agility, it is necessary to acquire a series of colorful new actions, only then the unknown ones are easily mastered on the basis of certain skills. In sports theory, the concept of "extrapolation", i.e., the ability to immediately formulate a reaction to a sudden situation (based on certain movement skills), is widely used. The greater the coordination capabilities of a person, the higher the level of implementation.

Naturally, most of the opportunities for coordination should be created in childhood and adolescence. The development of agility of the wrestler requires the performance of complex movements from the point of view of coordination; secondly, it consists in cultivating the ability to reorganize movement activities in accordance with the requirements of suddenly changed conditions. If it is necessary to accurately perceive one's movements in space and time, which is necessary for agility, stable movements, the ability to maintain balance, alternately exert and relax the muscles or, on the contrary, the ability to tense the muscles and so on. selective improvement of other similar characteristics is important. In the special scientific and methodical literature on wrestling, great importance is attached to the improvement of the means and methods of rapid strength training. However, it should be noted that the concepts of "quick - strength qualities" and "quick - strength training" have recently entered the theory and practice of sports wrestling as one of the types of manifestation of strength of an athlete.

CONCLUSION

In the practice of training highly skilled wrestlers, various exercises from general and special physical training tools are used to develop quick-strength qualities. This allows to increase quick-strength qualities within the framework of sports, that is, to improve physical qualities and movement technique at the same

time.

According to some authors, general developmental exercises can also be used for this purpose.

Other authors are supporters of the development of new non-traditional means of preparation.

A. N. Lens notes that many actions in the fight have a quick-power characteristic. Therefore, in the opinion of the author, the development of this quality should be carried out in an inextricable connection with the improvement of the technique of sports wrestling. The author recommends using special preparation tools for this.

Another researcher, B.I. Butenko, recommends performing exercises with weights of different weights at a pace from minimum to maximum in order to improve quick-strength qualities.

According to N.M. Galkovskii A.Z. Katulin, the most effective tool for the development of quick-strength qualities of wrestlers is basic exercises and competitions. The authors also recommend the use of special exercises that are close to the nature of the muscle tensions that appear in wrestling.

It can be said that in the process of preparing young wrestlers for competitions, it is very important to develop the quality of agility and train them in movement techniques.

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